

A NEW METHOD OF PREPARATION OF ANHYDROUS ACETATES OF RARE-EARTH ELEMENTS

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The anhydrous acetates of thorium, cerium and lanthanum have been prepared by the action of the respective nitrate on acetic anhydride. This method can be applied, in general, for preparation of the acetates of other rare earths and elements, the nitrates of which are partially soluble in acetic anhydride.

Preparation of anhydrous salts, particularly acetates of rare-earth elements, is not available in literature. In our investigation to effect the separation of the rare-earths, the salts of thorium, cerium(ous) and lanthanum were prepared by a method other than the usual one of dissolving the oxides, hydroxides or carbonates in acetic acid. By our method anhydrous salts are obtained, while the known methods furnish hydrated salts. The anhydrous salts of other elements, nitrates of which are partially soluble in acetic anhydride, can also be prepared by this method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cerium nitrate and acetic anhydride used were E. Merck chemicals. Thorium nitrate was of B. D. H. Analar quality. Lanthanum nitrate was prepared in the laboratory.

Acetic anhydride (10 c.c. in each case) was treated with the hydrated nitrates (3 g. each). The mixtures were heated over a sand-bath till the nitrous fumes had ceased to evolve. In case of thorium, the anhydrous acetate came down as a white granular powder. On heating the mixture containing cerium, at first a slightly yellow-coloured resinous mass separated which was found to contain nitrogen. On further heating and mechanically breaking up the resinous mass, a slightly yellowish precipitate settled down in granular form from the yellow solution. The yellow colour of the solution and the precipitate was mainly due to a portion of the cerium salt being in the ceric state (Patnaik and Panda, *Curr. Sci.*, 1956, 26, 287). A few drops of water were used to reduce the ceric salt which was produced in the mixture. The anhydrous cerous acetate was thus obtained as a white crystalline powder. The lanthanum salt was obtained in the same way as the cerium salt. The white precipitate, in each case, was filtered, washed with acetic anhydride and kept in a vacuum desiccator over solid NaOH to free them of solvents. The compounds on being tested were found free of nitrogen.

The oxide contents of the salts were obtained by ignition of weighed quantities of the salts in tared platinum crucibles over a Teclu burner. The results are recorded in Table I along with the calculated values. The acetate contents of the salts were determined by acidimetric titration with phenolphthalein as indicator. Weighed amount of the salt was dissolved in water in well-covered beakers and hydrolysed by boiling with

a standard NaOH solution (1.007 N/10, 30 c.c.). The precipitate was separated quantitatively by filtration. The filtrate was titrated with standard sulphuric acid to ascertain the volume of standard alkali consumed by acetic acid, liberated by hydrolysis. The alkali values are recorded in Table I along with that of the calculated values.

TABLE I

Expected compound.	Salt taken.	Weight of oxide.		Salt taken	Volume of alkali.	
		Calc.	Found.		Calc.	Found.
Th(C ₂ H ₃ O ₂) ₄	0.2890 g.	0.1631 g.	0.1614 g.	0.2150 g.	18.25 c.c.	18.30 c.c.
	0.2268	0.1280	0.1277	0.1580	16.82	16.85
Ce(C ₂ H ₃ O ₂) ₃	0.2283	0.1239	0.1221	0.1806	16.96	17.15
	0.1672	0.0907	0.0893	0.2006	18.85	17.90
Yb(C ₂ H ₃ O ₂) ₃	0.2940	0.1516	0.1460	0.1661	15.68	15.70
	0.2558	0.1320	0.1268	0.1669	15.73	15.90

The rare-earth nitrate in the reaction with acetic anhydride is converted finally into acetate, which being sparingly soluble in the solvent separates out as fine crystalline precipitates. Calculations indicate that hydrated or basic acetates are not formed in our experiments. Thus, the anhydrous acetates of the rare-earth elements have been prepared, as shown by the data recorded above.

It has been observed that the reaction proceeds in stages which cause the separation of intermediate resinous compounds during the preparation of lanthanum and cerium acetates. The elimination or deionisation of nitrate ion in acetic anhydride shows all the characteristics of a chain reaction. Further application of this reaction in the field of rare-earth chemistry is in progress and will be reported in a future.

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